

CLASSIC AND MODERN FAIRY TALES IN UKRAINIAN AND BRAZILIAN CONTEXTS

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Abstract

At this research, classic fairy tales were analyzed, and so where those produced today in an attempt to establish comparisons, observe divergences and convergences between them. As part of the analysis of the classic stories, the works Little Red Riding Hood, version of the Brothers Grimm (1980), translated from German into Ukrainian by Sydor Sakedona, illustrated by Valentina Melnythenko; version of Tchumak, edited in Toronto, Canada (1991) and illustrated by Noybacher (both in Ukrainian); Brazilian version, in Portuguese, of the Brothers Grimm present in the work *Histórias da Carochinha* (1993) with Mariza Dias Costa as an illustrator and the version of Perrault (1985) illustrated by Gustave Doré, were selected. From the modern fairy tales, “A moça tecelã” (A weaver girl) and “Entre a espada e a rosa” (Between the sword and the rose) were selected, stories present in the book *Um Espinho de Marfim e outras histórias* (An Ivory Thorn and other both stories) (2012) by Marina Colasanti, considered the largest producer of fairy tales in Brazil today. Based on the psychoanalytic theory of Bruno Bettelheim (1980), the stories were analyzed, also the female condition in the listed texts and the influences of the sociocultural context in which these works are inserted and the effects of meaning they generate were observed.

Keywords: Childrens’ Literature – Fairy tales – Woman